

Education in Times of Polycrisis: A Call for Radical Transdisciplinarity

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Abstract

Taking the case of early childhood education as an example, I argue for a necessary and possible paradigmatic shift in education scholarship and practice that embraces multiplicity, diversity, ambiguity, uncertainty and shared situated knowledge creation in response to a profoundly changed global context. Much of the thinking that shapes mainstream early childhood education and care today remains firmly grounded in 20th century certainties and teleological assumptions about linear progress, in child development as much as in educational policy and practice. Contours of a new paradigm are emerging as three interconnected fields of tension: First, the increasing recognition, by some international actors, of the complexity and systemic characteristic of early childhood education – contradicted by the persistent promotion of decontextualised approaches by others including OECD. Second, a blurring of boundaries between the Global South and North, in the context of rising inequality within countries. Third, the inability of dominant theories of early childhood education, grounded in disciplinary traditions from outside the field, to conceptualise present experiences and future directions. In conclusion I argue for the need and possibility of a trans-discipline of early childhood with profound implications for comparative work in the field.

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